

Domicile as a Personal Connecting Factor: An Assessment of Judicial Decision

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Abstract

Domicile is a legal terminology which discusses the connection between a personal and a sovereign state. It provides a dualistic character in private international law. It also conveys international unity with domestic acknowledgement and implementation as well as autonomous actions with the private affairs. This study aims to illustrate the function and nature of domicile as personal connecting factor in decision making to the choice of law. The qualitative approach has been chosen to discuss this study and to find out the data. This research has found that domicile originates with different foreign elements in sui generis because it depends on judiciary system, the nature of disputes and the covenants accompanied by the municipal policies of the particular country. This research paper also claims that every personal connecting factor can be applied globally in all similar circumstances as there are not much effectual deviations in their application. Thus, the outcomes of this study will help to identify the specific nature of domicile to cooperate judgment making in international legal system.

Keywords: Domicile; connecting factors; locality; personal law; living permanently.

Introduction

Domicile is one of the connecting factors ordinarily used in common law judicial systems (Dicey and Morris, 1993, p.115). It is basically known as a permanent place of dwelling of a person. It has a lawful connection between an individual and a locality ("US Legal Support", n.d.). McClean & Morris (1993) stated that domicile is a complex idea to explain, however, it gives a unique relationship between district system of law and a person. It confirms that no person can be without a domicile, even if they lack a permanent home (Singh, A., 2011, p. 1). Similarly, a person may have more homes, but cannot have more than one domicile at a particular time. A current domicile will be assumed to continue until

a change is proven on the balance of probabilities (“Law Teacher.net”, 2013). The proof of changing domicile of origin is heavy one (Dicey and Morris, 1993, p.122).

Domicile adjusts the legal capacity of a person at a particular time (“Law Note.net”, n.d.). For instance, the legality of an individual to marry and the distribution of property of a deceased are judged on the basis of domicile (“Law Teacher.net”, 2013). This example can be illustrated in such a way that a married man domiciled in Malaysia is under the jurisdiction of Malaysia for purposes of divorcing or dissolving his marriage. In this modern era, people are moving from one state to another. In the process of travelling, an individual is questing which will be applicable to him, his marriage, his contracts and so on. Then passport is generated to connect a person to a legal jurisdiction. Therefore, the domicile as personal connecting factor and it’s rationally under private international law is going to be explained profoundly.

Therefore, personal connecting factors are the situations which create relationship between event, thing, transaction, person and country. According to Falconbridge. J. D. (1954), they are defined by the *lex fori*. They support courts to identify the choice of law rule to administrate the immovable property of the person. They also assist court to decide under which legal system and within the jurisdiction of which country certain issues are to be determined. Similarly, connecting factors connect legal categories to applicable laws. Moreover, they create a natural connection between factual situation before court and particular jurisdiction (Kitime, E., n.d.). However, in most of the civil law countries the rule of domicile has been changed to nationality.

History and Definition of Domicile

Domicile is originated from the Roman law. The modern usage of domicile comes through the Canon law. According to a modern Canonist, “The term *domicilium* is derived from *domum colere*, to foster or inhabit the home. Domicile is not any place of residence but a place of habitual residence (“Law Teacher.net”, 2013).” It is pointed out from the common law history that the Diocese had authority over ordinary man in the Consistory Court in England. Thus, domicile of a man in a Diocese was recognised by his habitual residence (The Law Reform Commission, 1981, p.97). The Bishop who was habitual residence of the Diocese had jurisdiction in religious issues. The jurisdiction included probate and matrimonial matters even before the Matrimonial Causes Act 1857 and the Court of Probate Act 1857. English statutes characterised marriage of a man according to the place where he dwells. Thus, *domicilium* is a habitation or a dwelling which came from Diocese to Roman Canon law and to the English Canon law.

Dicey and Morris (1993) on the Conflict of Laws explained that the word “domicile” means a fixed, permanent and principal home to which an individual always intends to return. There is no unique definition of domicile. However, Stone. P. (1995) said that domicile consists of two fundamental elements that must

exist simultaneously such as physical presence in the jurisdiction and the intention to stay forever.

In law point of view, domicile is the status or attribution of being a permanent dweller in a specific jurisdiction. Domicile can be remained in a jurisdiction even after leaving it, if the person is maintaining sufficient links with that jurisdiction or is not displayed an intention to leave permanently (Davrados, N. A., 2017, p. 129). For example, it can be said that if person has not yet moved to a different state, or has not yet formed an intention to remain there indefinitely. In the case of *Waicker V Hume* (1858) 10 HLC 124, where appellant, a Scottish went to the East Indies and worked in a company for more than twenty years. He then resumed to Scotland and placed his name on the books of the municipality, acquired a house, married, did business, and became various societies' member. Later, he left Scotland in wrath, closed business, and removed his name from the books and societies, and declared he will never come back. After that he went to London and worked as a literature and tried to sale some of his books written on the Hindostanee language. A few years later, he left London to Paris to avoid some difficulties. However, he never made any declaration with respect to London. He died in Paris, having a will in the English form. The Court decided that appellant had lost his Scottish domicile and acquired an English domicile. In this case, Lord Chelmsford said in defining domicile that "A place is perfectly the domicile of an individual in which he has willingly fixed the dwelling of himself and his family, not for a mere special or temporary purpose but with a present intention of permanent home... (Essayist, 2013)." Lord Cranworth has also defined domicile in that case as, "Domicile means home, the permanent home; and if you do not understand your permanent home, I am afraid that no illustration drawn from foreign writers or foreign languages will very much help you to it (Dicey & Morris, 1993, p.115)."

Therefore, domicile is a place where a person resides permanently without any intention of moving. For jurisdictional purposes, domicile means a legal residence which is the place where a person has fixed dwelling with an intention of making it his/her permanent home (*Snyder v. McLeod*, 971 So. 2d 166). On the other hand, temporarily residing in a different place does not invalidate to have permanent home in a locality (*Abdrakhmanova, E. S., & Nyssanbekova, L. B.*, 2013, p. 1692).

Domicile plays a vital role in judicial decision making in a forum as it provides a pre-requisite presumption of the forum jurisdiction or assumption and acceptance of an overseas jurisdiction. It also confirms the basic rights of a person such as right to vote, right to hold public office and so on. Furthermore, it stipulates entitlement of numerous supports in respect of various needs such as ill-health or unemployment and liability to various forms of taxation ("Law Teacher.net", 2013). Moreover, domicile has a governing role in family and matrimonial property law. Lastly, Falconbridge. J. D. (1954) said that domicile ascertains the capacity of a person to make contracts, to validate a marriage, divorce, a will, matrimonial

causes, legitimacy and succession. Thus, domicile is very necessary to link a legal relationship of a person to a legal system.

The Rules of Domicile

Domicile is an idea of law which separates from the notion of permanent home. The components of domicile go beyond the requirements for the acquirement of a permanent home as it acquires a must intend to reside permanently or indefinitely (LEX 47, n.d.).

There are several rules that govern domicile as connecting factor in private international law. The rules can be classified in five major doctrines (“Law Teacher.net”, 2013). Firstly, a domicile is fixed for everyone. Domicile of origin is established by the law at the time of birth. Therefore, a legitimate child has the domicile of his father and an illegitimate child has the domicile of his mother. A foundling person has the domicile of the place where he is found. The domicile of origin remains until a new domicile is acquired by law. Secondly, no person has two domiciles at a time under international law. He may have more than one residence but one domicile will be established by looking at linking factors. Thirdly, it ties a person with a territorial law system. However, it is not necessarily the same principles for all the classes of persons because different rules will apply to different categories of people according to their religion, race or caste. Fourthly, an existing domicile will be assumed continuation. If anyone alleges the domicile of certain country, he must need to prove on the balance of probability. Fifthly, the domicile determines according to the English Common law unless there are some statutory exceptions. In *Re Annesley* [1926] Ch 692 case, the British man was domiciled in France. The issue was whether the conflict of laws of domicile will be decided based on English law or France. The court held that where a person is domiciled is determined according to English law which is *lex fori*.

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